

THE CONCEPT OF EXTREME MANAGEMENT THEORY

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In the article theoretical, methodological, and methodical questions of the formation of the new scientific direction in the system of management of the 21st century are opened: extreme management. Extreme management (extreme management) is considered a special type of management of the organization in uncertain conditions, uncertainty unpredictability, emergencies, and crises. Its main feature is the active inclusion of the administrative personnel in adopting extreme decisions.

Keywords: extreme management; methodology; administrative decisions; unpredictability; emergency and crises.

Introduction. In the practice of managing modern organizations, the so-called extreme management (extreme management) is becoming increasingly widespread. Today, extreme management is an effective tool for solving complex management problems in conditions of uncertainty and unpredictability, abrupt changes in the external and internal environment. The need to apply extreme management in everyday management practice required a serious rethinking and clarification of several provisions in the theory and practice of management.

What is extreme management?

Discussion. Extreme management is a special type of organization management based on the active involvement of all participants in the management process in the development and implementation of non-standard extraordinary decisions and high-risk actions in the shortest possible time. Such decisions should ensure the dynamic and sustainable development of the organization with constantly changing requirements for its activities, in the conditions of the external and internal environment in real time.

Extreme management is a flexible, dynamic management model for organizations of any type, the characteristics of whose development are turbulence, instability, uncertainty, unpredictability, and high speed of change.

The fundamental feature of extreme management is that it does not give managers a ready-made template and typical practical recommendations, but arms them, first of all, with an effective methodological toolkit for creating new creative solutions each time, failure which is unacceptable.

The philosophy of extreme management is based on a heightened sense of the need to search for and implement solutions to problems often beyond known possibilities. The implementation of this philosophy of extreme management requires that managers, along with high professionalism, demonstrate such signs of extreme as strong volitional and emotional qualities, and above all, courage, a high level of adrenaline in the process of making and implementing unusual solutions to non-standard problems.

Extreme management is based on a fundamentally new type of thinking and managing an organization - systemic and creative thinking. This type of thinking

corresponds to the nature of the external and internal environment of the organization in conditions of turbulence and constantly occurring changes, the need to make non-standard management decisions in a short time using previously unused management tools and methods.

The use of a systemic and creative approach in the process of making management decisions in extraordinary situations allows for synchronizing the state of the managed organization with the realities of unpredictability and chaos. This effect in extreme management is achieved through the use of the creative potential of management personnel and ensuring, on this basis, effective interaction between managers and the informal use of traditionally known processes, tools, methods, and technologies for making extreme management decisions. The conditions, tasks, and content of extreme management are fundamentally different from classical management. In classical management, the basic prerequisites taken into account in the process of making management decisions are the introduction of scientific and technological progress, the acceleration of the rate of change of generations of technological innovations; and the need for continuous improvement and updating of innovative products, technologies, etc. In extreme management, the main prerequisites for making management decisions are chaos, unpredictability, chance, constantly occurring changes in the external and internal environment of the organization; uncertainty, and surprise arising in the process of developing and implementing plans and programs for the development of the organization; a sharp reduction in the time frame for making and implementing management decisions. The features and specifics of classical and extreme management are presented in Table 1.

The most important task of extreme management is to reduce the period for generating, developing, and making extreme management decisions.

An extreme management decision is a decision that contains active, non-standard (sometimes shocking and uncopiable) measures and actions with a pronounced extreme focus and a high degree of risk, the main characteristics of which are high speed of adoption and effectiveness.

Extreme management also involves taking into account special areas, the main ones being:

Table 1.

Features and specifics of classical and extreme management (Source: Compiled by author)

Features of the type, conditions, and functions of management	Classical Management	Extreme Management
Type of management	Based on strategic (planned) foresight. Management is carried out stably, systematically, and consistently based on previously known and tested theoretical, methodological, and methodical provisions and techniques	Based on flexible, rapid response to unexpected changes. Management is reactive, quickly and flexibly responds to all changes in reality, regardless of previously adopted and approved plans
Conditions for making management decisions	Predictability, stability, regularity, consistency; bureaucratization, and the need to comply with clear rules and various types of scientifically based calculations. Forecasted, justified, and predictable variants of conditions for the development of events (optimistic, optimal, pessimistic)	Extreme conditions are unpredictability, uncertainty, disorder, and chaos. Creativity, innovation; high speed of non-standard decision-making, spontaneity, and improvisation, frequent use of the trial and error method
Planning	The main goal of planning is the systematic development and implementation of programs, plans, and projects to achieve justified goals with maximum efficiency	The main goal of planning is the rapid formation of an adaptive system of measures to solve problems with its constant adjustment to accomplish the tasks
Organization	A systematic step-by-step process of implementing programs, plans, and projects to achieve the intended results, aimed at its implementation with a minimum of deviations from the originally intended goals and parameters	The process of implementing programs, plans, and projects is carried out taking into account the extraordinary nature of rapidly changing conditions, adjustment of goals and objectives and changing deadlines, quantitative and qualitative indicators, performers, costs, resources, etc.
Motivation	Application of traditional methods of material and moral incentives to systematically achieve the intended results	Use of motivation tools and methods based primarily on emotional impulses of the soul, bursts of negative and positive emotions, awareness of one's superiority, ways and methods of solving a problem in an unusual way
Control	A strict control system that allows you to control (track) the degree of deviation of plans and programs implemented in stages, approved, and scheduled according to the schedule in terms of quantity, quality, timing, etc.	Flexible, differentiated, situational control, allowing for assessment of the degree of adequacy of the results obtained for their further adjustment taking into account the current realities

The most important features of extreme management decisions also include a high degree of flexibility and adaptability to constantly changing requirements and conditions, as well as a high level of creativity and innovation.

- the principle of anthropocentrism, which suggests that the extreme management process should serve the interests of people who primarily ensure success and creative solutions to problems, while classical management forces people to serve the process;

- the principle of creating a creative atmosphere and minimizing strict control over the management process (including the use of technologies, tools, methods, etc.) and delegating the control function to all its independent participants with the establishment of constant correction;

- the principle of the charisma of extreme managers who lead – “an extreme breakthrough team”, and not just management;

- the principle of conscious risk (the principle of

risky prudence), which suggests that in conditions of turbulence, uncertainty, and unpredictability, the use of traditional management approaches, tools, and methods can pose a danger to the organization;

- the principle of emancipation and improvisation of the manager in the process of making extreme management decisions. - the principle of constant search for balance in the process of using traditional and innovative management methods in extreme management, etc.

In addition to the above-mentioned equally important requirements, it should be noted: - synchronicity, adaptability, and automatism in the field of knowledge of management decisions;

- goals of iterative adjustment and ways of their implementation;

- anticipation of possible changes;

- taking into account the probabilistic consequences of making extreme decisions;

- implementation of constant express monitoring in extreme conditions.

In extremely established traditional management methods, they often do not work, or have low efficiency. All this requires the search and application of fundamentally new, previously untested tools and technologies for achieving management goals in extreme conditions.

Since extreme management is based on extreme actions, extreme management decisions, and countries with a high degree of risk, then, accordingly, its methods are not as authoritative as creative tools.

Such creative tools of extreme management include methods of analyzing extreme solutions ("PPKA analysis", "Creative online management", "Methods of developing problem situations", "Analysis of critical problems", etc.).

The stage-by-stage process of making extreme management decisions also has its characteristics, which is carried out in the following sequence: - express - assessment of an extreme situation;

- systemic and creative monitoring of the current problem;
- synchronized reduction and implementation of creative ideas and effective management decisions;
- assessment of the results and consequences of making extreme management decisions;
- adjustment of extreme management decisions based on express analysis of the extreme.

At all stages and phases of development and implementation of extreme management decisions, the management team works in the mode of emotional and psychological creative upsurge, constantly consistently new thoughts, and ideas offers non-standard measures aimed at achieving results. all results.

In extreme management, serious demands arise on the central figure of the management process - everyday life. The main task of a manager in extreme conditions is to preserve his principles and the mission of the organization, as well as to create an effective motivation system for all members of the management team. At the same time, the most important successful managers of the extreme type, determining the success of extreme management, are, first of all, self-discipline, positive energy, and charisma.

Managers of the extreme type are managers who take risks, make management decisions on the border, and also exceed the capabilities of an entrepreneur.

A manager of the extreme type is a manager who makes for himself the norm of what others consider extreme.

Effective application of extreme management in the process of solving non-standard problems requires compliance with several conditions that ensure high efficiency of its use.

Experience in the application of extreme management convincingly shows that the main reasons for failures in the process of making and implementing management decisions in extreme conditions are:

- the absence of extreme managers and managers in the "extreme breakthrough team" who provide the necessary training and ensure quality;

- focusing the attention of management teams only on technical and technological details without taking into account the constant changes in the environment of the organization, including in general economic, emotional, and psychological situations of expectations of the organization's personnel;

- low level of communication skills of management team members and, above all, lack of skills of effective direct interaction of management team members in a "live plan";

- excessive admiration, softness of management team members before the authority of leaders, strict execution of orders, inability to defend their point of view;

- bureaucracy and stereotypes in the management of the organization (excessive administration and bureaucratization, manifested in constant control in the form of reporting instead of activating the processes of high motivation of management personnel, aimed at the effective use of innate talents and abilities of personnel, the creation of effective innovative solutions);

- lack of trusting relationships between management team members.

The success of extreme management lies, first of all, in the ability to manage not so much the time and actions of the process participants, but the ability to manage creativity, creative energy, moods, and emotions of "extreme breakthrough teams".

A high level of creative potential, socio-psychological attitude, heightened feelings and emotions are important factors in making effective extreme management decisions in non-standard and extraordinary situations.

Effective extreme management takes place in flexible organizations with high adaptability to constantly changing conditions, organizations with a friendly high corporate management culture that allows for quick and effective switching from classical to extreme, from extreme to classical models of organizational management depending on the evolving needs and circumstances.

Specific models of extreme management for each organization are non-copyable models. Such models are individual, exclusive, and unique. In each specific case, they should be formed and implemented directly by the organization's management team with the involvement of relevant consultants and experts.

Conclusion. The need to train extreme managers with the necessary training and appropriate qualities, and to teach them effective technologies for solving management problems in extraordinary situations is becoming increasingly relevant today. Such training should be carried out in special advanced training programs, relevant seminars, and courses. The first experience of training extreme managers is available in many foreign countries (Poland, Bulgaria, the Netherlands, etc.).

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